

THE INFLUENCE OF BRAND IMAGE AND CONSUMER ATTITUDES ON BATIK BUNGO PURCHASE DECISIONS WITH PURCHASE INTEREST AS MEDIATION

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the influence of brand image and consumer attitudes. to direct and indirect batik purchase decisions mediated by buying interest in Bungo Batik consumers. The population in this study is batik consumers in Bungo. The number of samples used in this study was 116 people using the accidental sampling method with a non-probability sampling approach. Data collection method using questionnaires. Data analysis using regression analysis and path analysis. The results of this study show that brand image has a positive and significant effect directly on purchasing decisions, but consumer attitudes do not have a direct significant effect on purchasing decisions. Brand image and consumer attitudes have a positive and significant indirect influence on purchasing decisions through buying interest in Bungo batik consumers. The conclusion of this study is that it is proven that buying interest can mediate the influence of brand image and consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions

Keywords: Brand Image, Purchase Decisions, Purchase Interest

INTRODUCTION

Globalization and the current era of free trade are characterized by the increasing expansion of various products and services, causing business competition faced by companies to become increasingly fierce. With the existence of a free market, marketing is increasingly open and competition in the business world is increasingly fierce, this can be seen from the entry of imported products into the Indonesian market which is the

impact of Indonesia's agreement and signing of the Asean-China Free Trade Area (ACFTA). With this agreement, imported products are free to enter the Indonesian market. Marketers are required to be more careful in determining competitive strategies and taking advantage of existing opportunities. Marketers are required to be creative and innovative in order to attract consumer attention and attract consumer interest in buying the products offered.

The company uses various median marketing its products, one of the ways is as an effort to provide a good image to consumers (Udriyah et al., 2019). Brand image is an interpretation of the accumulation of various information received by consumers (Handayani et al., 2021). The image of a good company cannot be separated from consumers' views of what the company provides and what consumers feel. According to Kotler (2005) those who interpret are consumers and those who are interpreted are information. Image information can be seen from the logo or symbol used by the company to represent its products, where this symbol and logo is not only a differentiator from similar competitors but can also reflect the quality and vision and mission of the company.

Lendo's research (2013) which examines the influence of consumer attitudes on purchasing decisions concludes that consumer attitudes have a positive influence on purchasing decisions, meaning that the more positive the consumer attitude, the higher the consumer purchase (Handayani et al., 2021).

Consumer attitudes are formed from the consumer's tendency to take action on an object, the consumer's actions are to assess an object that he is interested in owning (Suwaryo et al., 2016). Attitude is a comprehensive evaluation and allows a person to respond in a favorable or unfavorable way to the object being assessed. Consumers who already have a positive attitude towards a product or brand will generate interest in purchasing that product or brand. (Pant et al., 2020) argues that interests play an important role in determining how people behave. The term purchasing interest has the meaning of purpose and is generally used to understand consumer goals in making a purchasing decision. The better the image of the product or brand,

Based on this description, purchasing interest in this research acts as an intervening variable that mediates brand image and consumer attitudes as independent variables with customer purchasing decisions as the dependent variable.

Research by Hidayati, et al (2013) examined the influence of brand image on buying interest and its influence on purchasing decisions, where the results of the research showed that consumer interest, desires and beliefs (purchasing interest) were greatly influenced by brand image and this would give rise to taking action. purchasing decision (Syapsan, 2019).

Purchase decisions can be defined as a process in which consumers evaluate various alternative choices and choose one or more of the necessary alternatives based on certain considerations (Istianingsih et al., 2020). Purchasing decisions made by consumers describe the level of influence of marketing efforts on a product, so marketers must know consumer behavior in determining purchasing decisions. It can be seen that purchasing decisions are individual activities that are directly involved in making decisions

to purchase products offered by the seller.

The aim of this research is to determine the influence of brand image and consumer attitudes on purchasing decisions directly or indirectly through purchasing interest, as well as to determine the influence of purchasing interest on purchasing decisions.

Based on the description above, the following hypotheses and research models can be arranged:

- H1: There is a positive and significant direct influence of brand image on purchasing interest.
- H2: There is a direct positive and significant influence on consumer attitudes towards purchase intention.
- H3: There is a positive and significant direct influence of brand image on purchasing decisions.
- H4: There is a positive and significant influence of consumer attitudes directly on purchasing decisions.
- H5: There is a positive and significant direct effect of buying interest on purchasing decisions.
- H6: There is a positive and significant influence of brand image indirectly on purchasing decisions through purchase intention.
- H7: There is a positive and significant indirect influence of consumer attitudes on purchasing decisions through purchase intention.

Based on the description above, the theoretical framework developed from this research can be seen in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

RESEARCH METHODS

The population in this research is batik consumers in Bungo. The number of samples used in this research was 116 people using the accidental sampling method with a non-probability sampling approach. The variables in this research are the brand image variable (X1) with indicators of quality, awareness, personality, self-image, consumer attitude variable (X2) with cognitive, affective and conative indicators, purchasing interest variable (Y1) with indicators of transactional interest, referral interest, preferential interest and exploratory interest, purchasing decision variable (Y2) with indicators of product

choice, dealer choice, brand choice and time choice. The data collection methods used are questionnaires and documentation. Data analysis techniques use path analysis (Path Analysis),

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity test

The results of the validity test are used to see the feasibility of an instrument.

Testing is valid if the sig. (2 tailed pearson correlation < 0.05). Results Test the validity of the questionnaire study explained on table following:

Table 1: Brand Image Validity Test Results, Consumer Attitudes, Purchase Intentions, and Purchase Decisions

No	Item Code	Sig value. (2 tailed) Pearson Correlation arithmetic	Sig value. (2 tailed) Pearson Correlation required	Information
1	X1.1	0,000	<0.05	Valid
2	X1.2	0.001	<0.05	Valid
3	X1.3	0.007	<0.05	Valid
4	X1.4	0.003	<0.05	Valid
5	X1.5	0,000	<0.05	Valid
6	X1.6	0.006	<0.05	Valid
7	X1.7	0,000	<0.05	Valid
9	X1.8	0.001	<0.05	Valid
11	X1.9	0,000	<0.05	Valid
12	X1.10	0,000	<0.05	Valid
13	X2.1	0.006	<0.05	Valid
14	X2.2	0,000	<0.05	Valid
15	X2.3	0,000	<0.05	Valid
16	X2.4	0,000	<0.05	Valid
17	X2.5	0,000	<0.05	Valid
18	X2.6	0.049	<0.05	Valid
19	X2.7	0,000	<0.05	Valid
20	X2.8	0.015	<0.05	Valid
21	X2.9	0.002	<0.05	Valid
22	Y1.1	0.027	<0.05	Valid
23	Y1.2	0.004	<0.05	Valid
24	Y1.3	0.004	<0.05	Valid
25	Y1.4	0,000	<0.05	Valid
26	Y1.5	0.015	<0.05	Valid
27	Y1.6	0.003	<0.05	Valid
28	Y1.7	0.011	<0.05	Valid
30	Y1.8	0.031	<0.05	Valid
31	Y1.9	0.002	<0.05	Valid
32	Y1.10	0,000	<0.05	Valid
33	Y1.11	0.020	<0.05	Valid
35	Y2.1	0.015	<0.05	Valid
36	Y2.2	0.045	<0.05	Valid
37	Y2.3	0,000	<0.05	Valid
38	Y2.4	0,000	<0.05	Valid

39	Y2.5	0.021	<0.05	Valid
40	Y2.6	0.002	<0.05	Valid
41	Y2.7	0.031	<0.05	Valid
42	Y2.8	0.011	<0.05	Valid
43	Y2.9	0.006	<0.05	Valid
45	Y2.10	0.029	<0.05	Valid
46	Y2.11	0.008	<0.05	Valid
47	Y2.12	0.001	<0.05	Valid
48	Y2.13	0.004	<0.05	Valid

Source: processed primary data, 2015

The results of the validity test on the research instrument showed that all were valid because the sig value was <0.05.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing was carried out to assess the consistency of respondents' answers. Something

A variable is said to be reliable if it provides value *Cronbach Alpha* > 0.60. The results of the research instrument validity test are explained in the following table:

Table 2: Brand Image Reliability Test Results, Consumer Attitudes, Purchase Intentions, and Purchase Decisions

No	Variable	The calculated Cronbach's Alpha value	Cronbach's Alpha value is required	Information
1	Brand Image	0.729	0.70	Reliable
2	Consumer Attitude	0.761	0.70	Reliable
3	Purchase Interest	0.715	0.70	Reliable
4	Buying decision	0.736	0.70	Reliable

Source: Processed data, 2015

Based on the test results, it can be explained that the variable brand image, consumer attitudes, purchase intentions, and purchase decisions are reliable with the results of Cronbach's alpha > 0.70.

Classic Assumption Test Results

Normality Test Results

Criteria For test normality use:

Kolmogorov- Smirnov Statistical Analysis

Data is said to be normal if the value of $KS > \alpha = 0.05$.

Table 3: Kolmogorov Smirnov Test Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		116
Normal Parameters, b	Mean	0.0000000
	Std. Deviation	3.47633662
Most Extreme Differences	absolute	0.065
	Positive	0.065
	Negative	-0.055
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.701
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.710
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		

Source: Processed data (2023)

Table 3 above shows that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov value is 0.701 with a significant value of 0.710 which is greater than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the regression model is normally distributed.

Multicolonearity Test Results

To detect this, it is done by looking at the tolerance value ≤ 0.1 and VIF value ≥ 10 , so it can be said that the regression model does not contain multicollinearity. The multicollinearity test results in table 4 are as follows:

Table 4: Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients			
		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Brand Image	0.792	1,263
	Consumer Attitude	0.610	1,639
	Interest Buy	0.512	1,955
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision			

Source: Data obtained (2023)

Table 4 shows the brand image tolerance value of 0.792, consumer attitude of 0.610, and purchase intention of 0.512, all of these values ≥ 0.1 and VIF brand image value of 1.263, consumer attitude of 1.639, and purchase intention of 1.955, all of these values < 10 , it can be concluded that the regression model does not have multicollinearity problems.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

One way to detect whether heteroscedasticity is present or not is to look at the results of the Glejser test.

Table 6: Heteroscedasticity Test with Glejser test

Coefficients ^a					
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
Model		B	Std. Error	Betas	Q
1	(Constant)	7,915	2,763		2,865
	Brand Image	-0.104	0.057	-0.189	-1.81
	Consumer Attitude	-0.062	0.077	-0.095	-0.799
	Purchase Interest	0.022	0.074	0.039	0.302
a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES					

Source: primary data processed, 2023.

The table above shows that none of the independent variables influence the dependent variable RES2 and the significance is above 5% so model regression No happen heteroscedasticity.

Model One Regression

Table 7: Model One Regression

Coefficients ^a					
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
Model		B	Std. Error	Betas	Q
1	(Constant)	8,539	3,407		2,506
	Brand_Image	0.315	0.066	0.328	4,754
	Consumer_Attitude	0.621	0.078	0.548	7,936
a. Dependent Variable: Interest_Buy					

Source: processed data, 2023

Based on table 7, it shows that the relationship between brand image and purchase intention has a positive relationship so that the relationship between brand image and purchase intention has a positive relationship. The brand image variable has a tcount of 4.754 with a significance level of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. It can be concluded that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. So,

H1 which states "There is a direct positive and significant influence of brand image on purchase intention received.

Path Analysis Test Results (path)

In this study, the data analysis method was used twice, namely linear regression and path analysis. Which will be explained as follows:

Regression Test

In this study, regression analysis was carried out twice, namely regression analysis to determine the relationship of the independent variables to the intervening variables and the second regression analysis to determine the relationship of the independent variables to the dependent variable.

The relationship between consumer attitudes and buying interest has a positive relationship. The consumer attitude variable has a tcount of 7.936 with a significance level of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. It can be concluded that consumer attitudes have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. So H2 which states "There is a positive and significant direct influence of consumer attitudes on purchasing interest" is accepted.

Regression model two

Table 8: Two Capital Regression

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	Model	B	Std. Error	Betas	Q	Sig.
1	(Constant)	19,694	4,280		4,601	0,000
	Brand_Image	0.354	0.089	0.342	3,985	0,000
	Consumer_Attitude	0.211	0.119	0.172	1,764	0.081
	Interest_Purchase	0.250	0.115	0.232	2,175	0.032
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase_Decision						

Source: processed data, 2023

Based on table 8, it shows that the relationship between brand image and purchasing decisions has a positive relationship. The brand image variable has a tcount of 3.985 with a significance level of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. It can be concluded that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. So H3 which states "There is a positive and significant direct influence of brand image on purchasing decisions" is accepted.

The relationship between consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions has a positive relationship. The consumer attitude variable has a tcount of 1.764 with a significance level of $0.081 \geq 0.05$, because the significance level of the consumer attitude variable is greater than 0.05, it can be concluded that consumer attitude has no influence on purchasing decisions. Then H4 which states "There is a positive and insignificant influence on consumer attitudes directly on purchasing decisions" is **rejected**.

The relationship between purchasing interest and purchasing decisions has a positive relationship. The purchase interest variable has a tcount of 2.175 with a significance level of $0.032 \leq 0.05$, it can be concluded that purchase interest has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. So H5 which states "There is a positive and significant direct influence of buying interest on purchasing decisions" is accepted.

Path Analysis

The path coefficient is calculated by making two structural equations, namely two regression equations that show the hypothesized relationship.

Where the Standardized coefficient beta brand image value is a b1 value of 0.328 and *standardized coefficient beta* consumer attitude is b2 value of 0.548 in the first regression model. Whereas in the second regression model, the standardized beta coefficient of brand image is b1 of 0.342, the standardized beta coefficient of consumer attitudes is b2 of 0.172, and the standardized beta coefficient of purchase intention is b3 of 0.232.

The value of $e_1 =$

$$\sqrt{1 - R^2} \text{ of } 0.715 \text{ and}$$

e_2 value =

$$\sqrt{1 - R^2} \text{ of } 0.807.$$

Direct and Indirect Influence of brand image on purchasing decisions through purchasing interest

Purchase intention as an intervening variable in relation to brand image (independent) to purchasing decisions (dependent). Interpretation of the results of path analysis can be done as follows:

Direct influence consumer attitudes towards decisions purchase	= 0.172
Indirect influence of consumer attitudes on purchasing interest on decisions purchase	(0.328 x 0.232) = 0.127
Total influence	<hr style="width: 50%; margin-left: auto; margin-right: 0;"/> = 0.299

indirectly on purchasing decisions through buying interest" is accepted.

Direct and Indirect Influence of consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions Through buying interest

Purchase intention as an intervening variable related to consumer attitudes (independent) to purchase decisions (dependent). Interpretation of the results of path analysis can be done as follows:

Direct influence of brand image on purchasing decisions. Indirect influence of brand image on purchasing interest on purchasing decisions = 0.342

$$(0.328 \times 0.232) = 0.076$$

The total indirect effect is greater than the direct effect $0.299 > 0.172$, then H6 which states "There is a positive and significant influence on consumer attitudes

$$\text{Total influence} = 0.418$$

The total indirect effect is greater than the direct effect $0.418 > 0.342$, then H6 which states "There is a positive and significant influence on Brand Image

indirectly on purchasing decisions through buying interest" is accepted.

The direct, indirect and total effects of each variable can be seen in table 11 as follows:

Table 11: Direct, Indirect, and Total Influence

No	Variable	Influence	Purchase Interest	Buying decision
1	Brand Image	Direct	0.328	0.342
		Indirect	-	0.076
		Total	-	0.418
2	Consumer Attitude	Direct	0.548	0.172
		Indirect	-	0.127
		Total	-	0.299
3	Purchase Interest	Direct	-	0.232
		Indirect	-	-
		Total	-	- 0.232

Source: processed data, 2023

The influence of brand image on purchasing interest

Based on the distribution of brand image indicators, personality indicators have the highest percentage. This indicates that a brand image can be formed when the target attitude, such as a brand, can be associated with personality traits that provide expressive or self-symbolic benefits for consumers. Self-expression can be a driver that influences consumer preferences and choices. The personality of a brand resides in the minds or perceptions of consumers that are formed directly or indirectly through direct experience in using a product or through marketing efforts. Brand personality is formed through brand names, symbols or logos, advertising, and product attributes.

Consumer buying interest in batik in Bungo, it is known that the exploratory interest indicator has the largest percentage in attracting consumer interest in buying batik in Bungo. Brand image can influence consumer buying interest in batik in Bungo, especially explorative interest, the behavior of someone who is always looking for information about the product they are interested in and looking for information to support the positive properties of the product that provide expressive benefits or self-symbol for consumers.

The research results are in accordance with research conducted by (Handayani et al., 2021) which explains that brand image has a positive influence on consumer purchase intention, states that the more positive the brand image, the higher the purchase intention and concludes that batik consumers in Bungo in this study pay attention to brand image to attract their buying interest.

The influence of consumer attitudes on purchasing interest

Consumer attitudes have a significant influence on consumer buying interest in Batik at Bungo, this means that consumer attitudes that are formed can affect consumer buying interest. If a positive attitude is formed in the minds of consumers, the consumer's desire to buy batik increases, and vice versa. Cognitive attitude indicators have the largest percentage in the distribution of consumer attitude indicators which indicate consumer attitudes are formed from the tendency of consumers to take action against attitude objects, in this case, batik products. The affective attitude indicator has a low percentage in the distribution of consumer attitude indicators which indicates that the overall evaluation and evaluation of consumers related to the feelings and emotions of a consumer towards batik products have a small role. The formation of consumer attitudes can influence consumers' buying interest in batik in Bungo, meaning that the majority of

batik consumers in Bungo are always looking for information about the products they are interested in and tend to take action towards batik products in accordance with their attitudes. This research is also in accordance with research conducted by (Hasan et al., 2021) who examined the influence of consumer attitudes on buying interest and found that buying interest was influenced by consumer attitudes, the more positive the consumer's attitude, the higher the consumer's buying interest. **Influence brands image to decision purchase**

Brand image has a significant influence on the purchasing decisions of Batik consumers in Bungo, the majority of Bungo batik consumers pay attention to the image of the product they will buy. The lowest percentage of indicators is the awareness indicator. Batik marketers at Bungo must also pay attention to consumers in making batik purchasing decisions. Positive image and brand awareness will play an important role in forming the initial perception in the minds of consumers. The better the image or the greater the consumer awareness of the brand (awareness) will encourage potential consumers to buy batik products from a brand rather than other brand products because consumers are more familiar with the brand's batik products.

Consumer purchasing decisions towards batik in Bungo, it is known that the brand choice indicator has the largest percentage in purchasing decisions for batik in Bungo. Brand image can influence consumer purchasing decisions, especially in brand choice decisions, meaning that consumers prefer one brand for one product among other brands of similar products. The brand choice taken by the consumer is the consumer's belief about the ability of a product compared to products with other brands.

This research is in accordance with research conducted by (Chen et al., 2016) who examined the effect of brand image on purchasing decisions, explaining that brand image has a positive and significant influence on consumers' desire to decide to buy a product, explaining that brand image has a positive influence on purchasing decisions. A positive influence can be interpreted as meaning that the more positive the brand image, the higher the consumer purchasing intensity of a product.

The influence of consumer attitudes on purchasing decisions

Consumer attitudes have no influence which is significant for consumer purchasing decisions regarding batik products in Bungo, this means that the consumer attitudes formed do not influence consumer purchasing decisions. The results of questionnaires that have been answered by consumers show that the majority have a good attitude towards batik in Bungo, but this does not necessarily improve consumer decision making to buy Bungo batik. The age of consumers is dominated by the productive age and the majority of respondents are women, which means attitudes are not given much attention in purchasing decisions. Consumers who have a good attitude towards batik in Bungo will not necessarily make a decision to buy, there are many other factors that consumers pay attention to in their decision to buy Bungo batik.

This research is in accordance with research conducted by (Dwivedi et al., 2020) which states that consumer attitudes do not influence purchasing decisions and concludes that purchasing decisions for formula milk are not influenced by consumer attitudes.

The influence of purchasing interest on purchasing decisions

Purchase interest in this research has four indicators consisting of transactional interest, referral interest, preferential interest and exploratory interest, namely showing good criteria for the statements given. The highest percentage is exploratory interest where batik consumers in Bungo want to always look for information about the products they are interested in and look for information to support the positive qualities of the product for consumers. Meanwhile, the lowest percentage is preferential interest, meaning that batik consumers in Bungo do not have a primary preference for the product in their purchasing interest. This preference can only be changed if something happens to the preference product. This means that batik marketers in Bungo must increase consumer buying interest by providing benefits that consumers can feel directly from their products,

Purchasing decision variable, it is known that the decision indicator for brand choice has the largest percentage, this indicates that batik consumers in Bungo pay attention to the batik products they will buy based on the image of the brand itself. Consumer associations with brands that can provide expressive or symbolic benefits for consumers, and are also related to the formation of the brand itself such as an easy-to-understand brand name and a good logo or motto. Purchase intention can affect decision making, especially because there are needs that must be met, consumers will seek information about the product they will choose, which means they are in the stage of having interest before finally making a buying decision.

The influence of brand image on purchasing decisions through purchase intention

Based on the research results it is proven that the total effect of brand image on the purchasing decision process through purchase intention is greater than the direct effect of brand image on the purchasing decision process, then buying interest is able to mediate the effect of brand image on purchasing decisions in a positive and significant way. Purchase intention is able to mediate brand image on purchasing decisions because with Bungo being known as the city of batik, then the variety of types of batik offered at Bungo also varies which can increase consumer buying interest, as evidenced by the percentage level of explorative interest indicators where batik consumers at Bungo want to always looking for information about the product they are interested in and looking for information to support the positive properties of the product for consumers.

Brand image that Bungo batik has and is attached to the consumer's perception that it is good, it will increase consumer awareness of the brand, which will ultimately influence consumer decision making. Brand image is strengthened when consumers have high interest and will decrease if consumers have less interest in the product. Consumers who are predominantly of productive age and already have jobs will think about various factors in making purchasing decisions, based on the distribution of variables in purchasing decisions, brand choice indicators have the largest percentage, so it is important to form a good image in the minds of consumers. Consumer awareness of brands (awareness) is also an important factor or indicator,

The influence of consumer attitudes on purchasing decisions through purchase intention

Based on the results of the study it is proven that the total effect of consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions through purchase intention is greater than the direct effect of consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions, then buying interest is able to mediate the effect of consumer attitudes on purchasing decisions in a positive and significant way. Purchase intention is able to mediate consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions because of consumer knowledge about the information on batik products provided, then affective factors or emotional feelings of consumers who like the combination of colors and patterns of Bungo batik and as an action that indirectly participates in preserving the cultural values of batik. itself can increase consumer buying interest, which is proven by the percentage level of exploratory interest indicators where batik consumers in Bungo want to always look for information about the products they are interested in and look for information to support the positive qualities of these products for consumers. The more positive the attitude

Consumers then have a tendency to choose and buy the product they like. Buying interest will then influence consumer purchasing decisions as seen from the introduction of problems and needs, consumers will look for information about the product they want to buy, from this the consumer will have an interest in buying before finally the consumer evaluates alternatives and makes decisions about the product he will buy. .

Consumer attitudes that are formed based on the learning process are displayed by the existence of positive perceptions attached to the minds of consumers, it will increase consumer awareness to take action in this case to buy or not buy an object of attitude which means the batik product of choice, which in the end will influence consumer decision making.

Consumer attitudes are strengthened when consumers have high interest and will decrease when consumers have less interest in the product. Consumers who are dominated by productive age and have jobs will think about various factors in making purchasing decisions, based on the distribution of variables in purchasing decisions, the dealer choice indicator has the lowest percentage, means that the choice of place where consumers will determine the purchase of a product will be purchased less attention by consumers. In this case, marketers must know how consumers choose the place of sale that consumers want. So it is important to form a good positive consumer attitude in the minds of consumers.

The positive attitude that is formed is also an important factor or indicator, because it indicates that consumer decision making in purchasing is also influenced by a good experience which they feel will form a positive consumer attitude towards Bungo batik products. So it is important to form a good positive consumer attitude in the minds of consumers.

The positive attitude that is formed is also an important factor or indicator, because it indicates that consumer decision making in purchasing is also influenced by a good experience which they feel will form a positive consumer attitude towards Bungo batik

products. So it is important to form a good positive consumer attitude in the minds of consumers. The positive attitude that is formed is also an important factor or indicator, because it indicates that consumer decision making in buying is also influenced by good experiences that have been felt to form positive consumer attitudes towards Bungo batik products.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The conclusions in this study proved that there is a positive and significant influence of brand image and consumer attitudes on purchase intention, this means that the more positive the brand image and consumer attitudes, the higher consumer buying interest. There is a positive and significant influence of brand image and purchase intention on purchasing decisions, this means that the more positive the brand image, and the higher the purchase intention, the higher the consumer purchasing decision, but consumer attitudes do not affect purchasing decisions, meaning that the positive attitude that consumers have has not certainly makes consumers make purchasing decisions, consumers only have a positive attitude towards Bungo batik products, but do not influence their decisions. There is a positive and significant influence of buying interest on purchasing decisions, this means that the higher the purchase intention, the higher the consumer purchasing decision. There is a positive and significant influence of brand image on purchasing decisions through purchase interest. This means that the more positive the brand image, the higher the purchase interest, which in turn will influence the purchase decision, so that purchase interest is able to mediate the relationship between brand image and purchase decisions. And there is a positive and significant influence on consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions through buying interest. This means that the better the consumer's attitude towards Bungo batik, the higher the buying interest will be, which in turn will influence the higher level of consumer purchasing decisions, so that buying interest is able to mediate the relationship between consumer attitudes towards buying decision. There is a positive and significant influence of brand image on purchasing decisions through purchase interest. This means that the more positive the brand image, the higher the purchase interest, which in turn will influence the purchase decision, so that purchase interest is able to mediate the relationship between brand image and purchase decisions.

And there is a positive and significant influence on consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions through buying interest. This means that the better the consumer's attitude towards Bungo batik, the higher the buying interest will be, which in turn will influence the higher level of consumer purchasing decisions, so that buying interest is able to mediate the relationship between consumer attitudes towards buying decision. There is a positive and significant influence of brand image on purchasing decisions through purchase interest. This means that the more positive the brand image, the higher the purchase interest, which in turn will influence the purchase decision, so that purchase interest is able to mediate the relationship between brand image and purchase decisions. And there is a positive and significant influence on consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions through buying interest. This means that the better the consumer's attitude towards Bungo batik, the higher the buying interest will be, which in turn will

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And there is a positive and significant influence on consumer attitudes towards purchasing decisions through buying interest. This means that the better the consumer's attitude towards Bungo batik, the higher the buying interest will be, which in turn will influence the higher level of consumer purchasing decisions, so that buying interest is able to mediate the relationship between consumer attitudes towards buying decision.

The managerial implementation of the results of this research should be for producers and marketers to develop product innovation, so that a positive image is formed. The better the image or the greater consumer awareness of the brand (awareness) will encourage potential consumers to buy a product because consumers are more familiar with the brand's products. Regarding the choice of supplier or location, improvements should be made, especially in the spatial sector for kiosks, a neat and clean canteen environment will give a better image that this object is orderly and beautiful. Then create adequate and appropriate facilities so that visitors are comfortable when shopping and regarding the lack of information about batik.

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